

*N*₁-phthalimido acetyl/2-propionyl-N₈-aryl thio-ureas : To a 250 ml three necked flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer and reflux condenser and a dropping funnel, were charged 0.01 mole of phthalimido acetyl/2-propionyl chloride and 30 ml dry benzene. To the vigorously stirred solution was added drop by drop a solution of 0.01 mole of ammonium thiocyanate in 10 ml dry benzene over a period of 15 min. The isothiocyanate thus obtained was made to react without isolation with appropriate amine (0.01 mole) by refluxing for 3 hr. The mixture was poured in crushed ice and the crude product was filtered and washed several times with water. The product was recrystallised from ethanol.

The m. p., yield and analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Insecticidal activity : The insecticidal activity was evaluated against adult male flies (*Musca domestica* L.) as the test insect following the method of Nash¹⁹. The compounds were dissolved in acetone and the acetone solution applied at a dosage of 0.001 mole per fly. With every sample, three experiments, each consisting of 20 flies were performed and the treated insects were kept under observation for 24 hr. The average results were recorded taking Heptachlor and Toxaphene as standard.

Compound No. 13 only at 1% concentration afforded 50% mortality against *Musca domestica* L.

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Studies on Hydroxamic Acids : Part II. Separation and Quantitative Determination of Yttrium with N-m-Tolyl-m-Nitrobenzohydroxamic Acid

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IN connection to our earlier work¹⁻⁸, this communication deals with the separation and quantitative determination of yttrium with N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid. Experimental results and discussion given below.

Experimental

Chemicals : All the chemicals used were of the G.R. and AnalaR grade of E. Merck and B. D. H. respectively.

Reagent : The reagent N-m-Tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid was synthesized by the procedure recommended by Agrawal and Tandon⁶, m. p. 118° (reported 118°). The purity of the reagent was established by elemental analysis T. L. C., I. R. and U. V. Spectra.

Metal solution : The aqueous stock solution of yttrium was prepared by dissolving 0.3830 g of yttrium nitrate hexahydrate in 100 ml of distilled water and its final concentration was determined volumetrically⁷.

Masking agent : A 1% of masking agent solutions of KCN, Citrate-oxalate and Mg-EDTA were prepared by dissolving their requisite amount in distilled water.

Procedure

In a litre beaker an aliquot of yttrium solution and 500 ml distilled water were heated to 60° on a water bath. Then 20 ml of the reagent solution in ethanol was added dropwise, with constant stirring. The desired pH for the precipitation of yttrium (5.7 to 6.5) was adjusted by using 0.1M solution of ammonium hydroxide and of 0.1 M nitric acid. The granular precipitate so obtained was digested for 30 min. on a water bath, filtered through a sintered glass crucible

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(G4) and was washed thoroughly with hot water. The precipitate was washed finally with 10 ml of 20% aqueous-ethanol. The complex was dried at 120° and weighed directly as $[C_{14}H_{11}N_2O_4]_3 Y$.

Separation of yttrium from diverse metal ions : A portion of standard solution of yttrium was mixed with foreign metal ions and diluted to 500 ml. The pH was adjusted to 5.7 to 6.5 with dilute ammoniumhydroxide and dilute nitric acid. A 10 ml of KCN solution was added and contents were heated to 60° on waterbath, and the precipitation was completed as before. This way, yttrium could be separated and determined in presence of Ag (I), Mn (II), Zn (II), Mg (II), Cd (II), Cu (II), Mg (II), and Ga (III).

Yttrium could be separated and determined quantitatively in presence of Pb(II), Pd(II), Bi(III), Ti(IV) and Zr(IV), if 10 ml. of citrate-oxalates were used as masking agent instead of KCN.

Al(III), V(V), Mo(VI) can be masked if Mg-EDTA is used as masking agent.

Separation of yttrium from Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III) and La(III) was made by the pH adjustment of the solution, since these rare earths precipitated in alkaline medium.

Results and Discussions

The results of the present investigation are shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF YTTRIUM

Yttrium taken mg	Yttrium found mg	Error
4.32	4.33	+0.01
8.64	8.63	-0.01
12.96	12.98	+0.02
17.28	17.29	+0.01
21.60	21.58	-0.02

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF YTTRIUM FROM DIVERSE IONS

Yttrium taken (mg)	Foreign metal ions (mg)	Masking Agent	Yttrium found (mg)
6.48	Ag(I) (60)	Cyanide	6.47
10.80	Mg(II) (80)	"	10.81
8.64	Zn(II) (80)	"	8.63
12.96	Mg(II) (80)	"	12.97
8.64	Cd(II) (80)	"	8.64
8.64	Cu(II) (80)	"	8.65
10.80	Hg(II) (60)	"	10.81
12.96	Pb(II) (80)	Citrate+Oxalate	12.95
8.64	Pd(II) (60)	"	8.63
8.64	Ga(III) (100)	Cyanide	8.65
6.48	Bi(III) (80)	Citrate+Oxalate	6.47
10.80	Al(III) (100)	Mg-EDTA	10.81
8.64	La(III) (80)	"	8.65
12.96	Pr(III) (80)	"	12.97
12.96	Nd(III) (80)	"	12.95
12.96	Sm(III) (80)	"	12.97
12.96	Ti(IV) (100)	Citrate+Oxalate	12.95
12.96	Zr(IV) (100)	"	12.95
12.96	V(V) (80)	Mg-EDTA	12.94
12.96	Mo(VI) (100)	"	12.96

The complex was found fairly soluble in dioxane, and chloroform but sparingly soluble in carbon-tetrachloride, and diethyl ether. It is decomposed when treated with concentrated mineral acids.

Analysis : The analytical result shows the composition of the complex as $[C_{14}H_{11}N_2O_4]_3 Y$.

Calculated C = 55.93% ; H = 3.68% ; N = 9.31% ;
Y = 9.85% ;

and found C = 55.94% ; H = 3.67% ; N = 9.28%
Y = 9.87%.

Effect of pH : For carrying out the separation and gravimetric determination of yttrium in the different pH values with all the other factors identical revealed that they are irrespective at pH 5.7 to 6.5.

Masking agent : Experimental studies show that the presence of excess of KCN and Mg-EDTA did not interfere with the precipitation of yttrium while the excess of citrate-oxalates inhibited the precipitation.

Precision and accuracy : The present study for gravimetric determination of yttrium has the relative average error ± 0.02 .

I. R. spectra : The infrared spectra of the reagent N-m-T-m-NBHA, as a mull shows the peaks at 3289, 1600 and 917 cm^{-1} , due to stretching vibrations of O-H, C=O and N-O groups respectively. On complex formation the peak at 3289 cm^{-1} disappears owing to the replacement of H^+ by the metal ion, indicating the co-ordination of oxygen atom to the metal ion. If the hydroxyl group were bonded to the metal through a lone pair of electrons and still retained the hydrogen atom, the O-H stretching frequency would be altered. The spectrum of the complex showed no appearance of such a new peak, thus confirming the coordination of metal to the oxygen atom.

The carbonyl stretching vibration shifts to lower frequency at about 1555 cm^{-1} , owing to the bonding of the carbonyl oxygen atom to the metal ion. The N-O stretching vibration at 917 cm^{-1} is unaltered except its intensity, which is increased.

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